

ISic1129

I.Sicily inscription 1129

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Panhormus

Place of origin (modern)

Palermo

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Ἰούλιος Ἰοῦστος

2. ἔζη(εν) ἔτη λ

3. καὶ ἐβίω[cen---]

3a. []

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492742

EDR 140880

EDCS 39102286

PHI 140614

PHI 175755

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. *Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0310 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

Manni Piraino, M.T. 1973. *Iscrizioni greche lapidarie del Museo di Palermo. Sikelika 6.* Palermo. At 150

Ferrua, A 1941. *Epigrafica sicula pagana e cristiana. Rivista di archeologia cristiana.* 18: 151-243. At 230 no.123

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic1129. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4351573>